

New hypothesis about double or multiple planetary nebulae.

Part I: What is this?

So, we all know about double or multiple stars systems, what about double or multiple planetary nebulae systems when stars like our sun in this system, dies and create planetary nebulae? It's an interesting hypothesis, because double or multiple star systems it's mostly part of the universe than just stars without companions, so it's a very good argument for my hypothesis. What about the chance of finding an object like that? We need to find a system like that and just observe.

Part II: Is it possible?

The answer is - Yes, and I have facts and arguments.

- I. The universe mostly has double systems then just one star or planet system. Here is an article about this: [A Survey of Stellar Families: Multiplicity of Solar-Type Stars](#).
- II. It is known that there are many double systems similar to the sun, which increases the chance of the emergence of hypothetical double planetary nebulae. For example, the system **'16 Cygnus'** in the constellation Cygnus consists of two sun-like stars and a red dwarf.

Part III: Conclusion.

We have facts, we even have a system with stars like the Sun, which serves as a compelling argument in favor of the existence of double planetary nebulae. However, we either need to find them or observe double or multiple systems like the Sun, then this hypothesis may possibly become a reality.